

**A STUDY ON CRIME AWARENESS AMONG THE SECONDARY
STUDENTS OF STANDARD 8TH OF MULUND****Dr.Kusum Vijaykumar Chaudhari***Chembur Sarvankash Shikshanshastra Mahavidyalya, Chembur, Mumbai-71***Introduction:**

A generalized definition of cybercrime may be “unlawful acts wherein the computer is either a tool or target or both”. The other definition could be, “cyber crime is a form of crime where the internet or computers are used as a medium to commit crime”. According to Pavan Duggal, Supreme Court Advocate and Cyber Law expert, “Any criminal activity that uses a computer either as an instrumentality, target or a means for perpetuating further crimes comes within the ambit of cyber crimes.”

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Now a day, there is a sea change in the world due to advancement in science and technology. This materialistic and modern world has created a number of problems which has put the world endanger; one of them is cyber crime that is emerging as a serious threat in the world. The increased reliance of individuals/organizations/students on cyber resources (blogs/forums, e-dictionary/book, meta search engines, database-journals/libraries/documents, e-mail, website, web based application, search engines) has resulted in to a corresponding increase in the cybercrime (assault by threat, pornography, contraband, laundering, stalking, terrorism, theft, fraud, credit/debit card fraud etc.). These cyber resources especially internet has a significant impact on our lives and no doubt; today, it is the need of the hour. Welsh (2011) [10] call today generation is “digital natives” or the “I-Generation”. New generation is growing up with computers and which is bringing joy in their lives but also with a number of dangerous problems due to unawareness about cyber crime. Pandey (2012) [7] stated that lack of awareness about internet and low level of internet security is fast making a heaven for cybercriminals. The most targeted groups of this problem are students; they are not aware

about the cyber crime and unknowingly they do crime which leads them to criminal. This technology becomes a more prevalent part of education system which cannot be ignored and the role of teachers is not only to teach the students but aware them about the social and other problems and teach them how to overcome on these problems special cyber crimes and how to implement these resources in order to be successful careers and happy life. The students must be aware that what the best use of cyber resources is for him/her and how to protect from the hazards of cyber crime.

1.2 Title of The Problem:

A study on crime awareness among the secondary students of standard 8th Mulund Vidyamandir, Mulund.

1.3 Need Of The Study:

Every minute, on an average, nearly 80 people in India fall prey to some form of cybercrime and the awareness initiatives in place to prevent them are not enough, to add to it further, across the globe, India tops in cases of spam attacks, and stands third in cases of computer virus attacks and overall cyber threats. In such a scenario, the field of education has a greater role to play to create awareness among people on the nuances of cyber crimes and the deep impact it can cause.

According to web dictionary Cyber Crime is, “illegal activities committed over the internet.” The web has opened up many avenues for us and the world is working towards making our lives easier and worthwhile. Computer education became inevitable aspect of our school curriculum. We have started training young children for the future digital world. In doing so, we have paid very little attention to the security risks that we were taking. Computers and the internet are being misused for unlawful activities like e-mail espionage, credit card fraud, spam, software piracy, spreading of viruses and so on, which invade our privacy and offend our senses. Criminal activities over internet are on the rise. The young children unknowingly violate copyright laws or are a prey to plagiarism. The cybercrime today is the latest and perhaps the most complicated problem in the cyber world.

The present research aims to find out if the young students are even aware of the basic Netiquettes and the elementary cyber laws. If the children are introduced to concept of plagiarism, and ethical use of internet, probably we will have less cases to deal with in the

future.

1.4 Significance Of The Study:

- 1) Research is a systematic search for an answer to a question or a solution to a problem.
- 2) To create awareness among the students about cyber crime.
- 3) Studying the cyber awareness will lead to self-development and a safe society in future.
- 4) The research topic has its relation with the quality of life we live in and will be useful to the branch of cyber criminology

1.5 Objectives of The Research:

- 1) To find out internet usage of the secondary students.
- 2) To find out cyber crime awareness among the secondary school students using Cyber crime awareness scale by Dr.Rajasekar.
- 3) To identify the gaps in awareness about the cyber-crimes and suggest remedial measures.
- 4) To disseminate the relevant information to concerned authorities.

1.6 Hypothesis:

A **hypothesis** is a tentative statement about the relationship between two or more variables. It is a specific, stable prediction about what you expect to happen in a **study**. Let's take a closer look at how a **hypothesis** is used, formed, and tested in scientific **research**.

There is no relationship between the educational level of secondary students of standard 8th and the awareness of cybercrime among them.

1.7 Variables:

A **variable** is defined as anything that has a quantity or quality that varies. The dependent **variable** is the **variable** a researcher is interested in. An independent **variable** is a **variable** believed to affect the dependent **variable**. Confounding **variables** are defined as interference caused by another **variable**.

A variable is anything that can vary, i.e. changed or be changed, such as memory, attention, time taken to perform a task, etc. Variable are given a special name that only applies to experimental investigations. One is called the dependent variable and the other the independent variable.

A) Independent Variable: scale on cyber crime

B) Dependent Variable: Students awareness on cyber crime

C) Control Variable:

- 1) Subject and Topic
- 2) 100 Students of 8th Standard of Mulund Vidyamandir.

1.8 Operational Definition:

1. **Effect:** An impact created on the learning of the student when new way of teaching is implemented.
2. **8th standard students:** As per the Indian system of Education which is 10+2+3. The eight standards is the eighth grade of the higher primary section.
3. **Cyber Crime:** cyber crime is a form of crime where the internet or computers are used as a medium to commit crime.
4. **Awareness:** the quality of being aware about knowledge or understanding that something is happening or exists.
5. **School:** School is an institution which aims at holistic and all round development of the student. Nurturing values and giving a rich experience which last forever.

1.9 Scope Of The Study:

- 1) The present research includes cybercrime awareness.
- 2) The present research includes 8th standard students.
- 3) The present research is conducted for academic year 2019-2020.
- 4) The awareness about cybercrime will be created among other students, Relatives, friends and society at large.

1.10 Limitations Of The Study:

- 1) The present research includes only awareness on cybercrime subject.
- 2) The present research includes only 8th standard students.
- 3) The present research is conducted only for academic year 2019-2020.
- 4) The present research is only for 100 students of 8th standard of Mulund Vidyamandir

1.11 Selection Of Research Method:

For the present research survey method has been used. Including in-person and telephone interviews, mailed and online questionnaires.

1.12 Research Procedure:

The present study implements the awareness of assessing cybercrime among STD VIII

students.

Research Design

A research design is a plan and strategy of investigation conceived to obtain answers to the research problem. The study on “Cybercrime Awareness among Eighth Standard Students in Mulund Vidyamandir”, has been attempted for identifying the awareness level among the children.

Sample Location

The Students studying in Std. VIII in Mulund Vidyamandir have been selected for the present study.

Sampling Techniques

A sample as the name implies is a smaller representation of a large whole. It is a small proportion of a population selected for Observation and Analysis. The sampling technique has been the random sampling lottery method, whereby 100 were selected from Mulund Vidyamandir

1.13 Tools Used For The Study:

Construction of tool

In this phase order to enhance reliability, accuracy, suitability, practicability of the information the researcher has used Questionnaire tool developed by Dr. Rajasekar for this research.

Test Administration Procedure:

- 1) To study the concept of cyber crime.
- 2) To use questionnaire tool developed by Dr. Rajsekar.
- 3) To take approval of the research guide for the same.
- 4) To take permission from the School Principal for conducting the research.
- 5) To select class of Mulund Vidyamandir, Mulund .
- 6) To distribute the questionnaire to students to solve it.
- 7) To calculate the raw score of each student.
- 8) To find out the mean and standard deviation of male student and female student group.
- 9) To analyze, and interpret the scores
- 10) To type and submit the report.

Statistical Techniques Used

- Mean
- Standard deviation
- T score
- Z score

Data analysis and interpretation:

The aim of present study is to find out the “**The Study of the crime awareness among the VIII std students of Mulund Vidyamandir, Mulund**” The investigator collected data from examining 100 students from 8th of Mulund Vidyamandir . The collected data are arranged properly, analyzed systematically and interpreted precisely.

When interpreting data, an analyst must try to discern the differences between correlation, causation and coincidences, as well as much other bias – but he also has to consider all the factors involved that may have led to a result. There are various data interpretation methods one can use.

The interpretation of data is designed to help people make sense of numerical data that has been collected, analyzed and presented. Having a baseline method (or methods) for interpreting data will provide your analyst teams a structure and consistent foundation. Indeed, if several departments have different approaches to interpret the same data, while sharing the same goals, some mismatched objectives can result. Disparate methods will lead to duplicated efforts, inconsistent solutions, wasted energy and inevitably – time and money.

Analysis And Interpretation Of Data:

TABLE NO: 1
TOTAL NUMBER OF STUDENTS

STUDENT (FEMALE)	STUDENT (MALE)	TOTAL
41 (41%)	59 (59%)	100

PIECHART NO: 1

Observation

Female Student for this research is 41% and male student is 59%

Interpretation

Male student for this research are almost equal to female student.

Finding

The difference between female and male student is 18%

TABLE NO: 2
ATTENDED COMPUTER CLASSES- FEMALE STUDENTS

	YES	NO
ATTENDED COMPUTER CLASSES	19(47.5%)	22(53.5%)

PIECHART NO: 2

Observation:

47.50% of female student attended computer classes and 53.50%female students did not attended computer classes.

Interpretation

Number of female students who attended the computer classes is almost the half of the total female students.

Findings

Female students who did not attended computer classes are11%more than attended female students.

TABLE NO: 3
HAVING OWN COMPUTER-FEMALE STUDENTS

	YES	NO
HAVING OWN COMPUTER	30 (73.18%)	11 (26.82%)

PIECHART NO: 3

Observation

73.18% of female student have their own computers and 26.82%female students did not have their own computers.

Interpretation

Numbers of female students who have the computers are more than the one who do not have computers.

Findings

Female students who have computer are thrice more than one who do not have computers.

TABLE NO: 4
ATTENDED COMPUTER CLASSES- MALE STUDENTS

	YES	NO
ATTENDED COMPUTER CLASSES	23 (38.98%)	36 (68.02%)

PIE CHART NO.4

Observation:

38.98% of male student attended computer classes and 68.02% male students did not attended computer classes.

Interpretation

No of male students who attended the computer classes is almost the half of the total.

Findings

Male students who did not attended computer classes are 29.04% more than attended students.

TABLE NO: 5
HAVING OWN COMPUTER -MALE STUDENTS

	YES	NO
HAVING OWN COMPUTER	43(72.88%)	16(27.12%)

PIE CHART NO: 5

Observation:

72.88% of male student have their own computers and 27.12% male students do not have their own computers.

Interpretation

Numbers of male students who have the computers are more than the one who do not have computers.

Findings

Male students who have computers are thrice more than one who do not have computers.

TABLE- : 6

BROWSING PERIOD- OCCASIONALLY

	FEMALE STUDENT	MALE STUDENT
OCCASIONALLY	18 (43.90%)	25 (42.37%)

PIE CHART NO: 6

Observation:

43.90% of female students browse occasionally while 42.37 % male students browse occasionally.

Interpretation

Browsing occasionally among male students and female students is the same.

Findings

Browsing occasionally among male students and female students each is less than 50%

TABLE: 7

BROWSING PERIOD- EVERY DAY

	FEMALE STUDENT	MALE STUDENT
EVERY DAY	23 (56.10%)	34 (57.63%)

PIE CHART NO: 7

Observation:

56.10% of female students browse everyday while 57.63 % male students browse every day.

Interpretation

Browsing everyday among male students and female students is almost the same.

Findings

Browsing everyday among male students and female students each is more than 50%

TABLE NO: 8
CYBER CRIME AWARENESS AMONG GIRL AND BOY STUDENTS

STUDENTS	NO OF STUDENTS	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	T - RATIO	SIGNIFICANT/NOT SIGNIFICANT
FEMALE	41	143.58	14.27	1.14	NOT SIGNIFICANT
MALE	59	149.25	16.85		

GRAPH NO: 8

Observation

The method used for testing of hypothesis for present study was 't' test

Interpretation

The mean of female student was 143.58 and male student was 149.25. Standard deviation for female student was 14.27 and male student was 16.85.

Findings

It was found that the mean score of female students (143.58) which is less than the mean scores of male students (149.25). The calculated t-value is 1.14 which showed that there is no significant difference between boy and girl students in respect of their attitude towards the cybercrime awareness

TABLE NO: 9
CYBER CRIME AWARENESS LEVEL

Sr. No	Raw Score Range	Z Score Range	T Score Range	No of Girl students	No of Boy students	Grade	Level of Cyber Crime Behavior
1	143 & above	2.04 & above	70.37 & above	20	40	A	Excellent Awareness
2	133 - 142	+ 1.31 to + 1.96	63.06 to 69.63	12	11	B	High Awareness
3	123 - 132	+ 0.57 to + 1.23	55.75 to 62.32	5	4	C	Above average awareness
4	108 – 122	‘ - 0.52 to +0.50	44.78 to 55.01	4	3	D	Moderate Average Awareness
5	99 – 107	-1.18 to – 0.60	38.20 to 44.05	0	1	E	Below Average Awareness
6	88 -98	-1.98 to 1.25	30.16to 37.47	0	0	F	Low Awareness

GRAPH NO: 9

SJIF Impact Factor 7.372

Peer Reviewed Journal

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Observation

Out of 59 male student's 40 male students and out of 41 female students' 20 female students have excellent awareness. 12 female students and 11 male students have high awareness. Above average awareness is found among 5 female students and 4 male students. Moderate average awareness is found among 4 female students and 3 male students. Below average awareness is only 1 in male student.

Interpretation

Excellent awareness among male students is more than female students. High awareness is almost the same. Only one male student is found below average.

Findings

The study states that majority of students have excellent awareness according to Dr. Rajsekar scale on cybercrime awareness.

Findings Of The Study:

The study comprises 59% percent male students and 49% percent female students belonging to of Mulund Vidyamandir, Mulund

The study comprises that 47.5% of female student and 38.98% of male student attended computer classes and 73.18% female student and 72.88% male student have their own computer. So the ratio of having own computer is same among female students and male students.

Browsing period occasionally of female student is 43.90% and male student is 42.37%. In comparison to this everyday browsing period is more among female student (56.10%) and male student (57.63%)

It was found that the mean score of female students (143.58) which is less than the mean scores of male students (149.25). The calculated t-value is 1.14 which showed that there is no significant difference between male and female students in respect of their attitude towards the cybercrime awareness.

According to the Dr Rajasekhar scale of cybercrime awareness out of 59 male students 40 male students and out of 41 female student's 20 female students have excellent awareness. 12 female students and 11 male students have high awareness. Above average awareness is found among 5 female students and 4 male students. Moderate average awareness is found among 4 female

students and 3 male students. Below average awareness is 1 in male student.

5.3 Educational Implications:

The result of the study can be usefully employed in school practice. The present study has the following educational implications for the school teachers, and students:

- 1) It can help the teacher to know about the level of awareness towards cybercrime in students.
- 2) The teacher can tell the students about the harmful effects of using internet without sufficient preventing measures.
- 3) The teacher can tell the students about safe internet browsing and protect themselves of being victims. To the lack of awareness towards cybercrime.
- 5) The students can protect themselves from hacking, phishing, spam, identity theft etc.

5.4 General Recommendation:

There are so many actions available to reduce Cyber Crime and cyber offence and out of which following are important such as-

- 4) It can help in decreasing the involvement of students in cybercrimes who do mistakes due

Legal Action: As far as legal action is concerned, the following actions may be helpful to reduce Cyber Crime and important to take into

Electronic Communications Privacy Act of 1986.

Federal Privacy Act of 1974.

Indian IT Act.

Communications Act of 1934 updated 1996.

Computer Fraud and Abuse Act of 1984.

Computer Security Act of 1996.

Economic Espionage Act of 1996.

Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996.

Personal Data Privacy and Security Act of 2007.

Data Accountability and Trust Act.

Identify Theft Prevention Act.

Data security Act of 2007

Awareness Building:

Awareness building is most important to reduce Cyber Crime and IT crime; thus

following things are essential to follow Creating changes in the password of the computing devices such as computers, search and networking systems, changes of the password of other services such as email, social networking site, and other service based site registered by the applicant or user. Reduction in use of email in cyber café and other places and computing devices. Open and communicating with the unknown computer and similar device.

Technological Backup:

Use of Anti Virus software and system in the computer system or when network or telecommunication Systems.

Use of internet safety tools, appropriate time and as per machine requirement.

Use of Good firewall and sophisticated Network Designing.

Keep off the Blue tooth and other RF devices [19].

5.5 Suggestions For Further Research:

No research can be the final word on a problem as every research cannot touch upon all the complex aspects of a problem in one attempt. In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following suggestions for further research in this area of study are being made:

- 1) Current study focused on Cyber Crime among one school. It needs to focus on other schools and emotional and motivational dependent variables such as attitude towards subjects, self-esteem, peer relations, social skills and motivation.
- 2) Are plicate study can be conducted at different grade levels, different environment → settings to evaluate effectiveness?
- 3) A study can also be conducted to compare and explore how cybercrime affect the students of various abilities on cognitive, emotional and motivational dimensions; as well as on cognitive and non cognitive dimension. The study can be repeated to compare the effectiveness of various → strategies under cybercrime in different situations and contexts like – rural, urban, male, female students and mixed genders at different levels, which may be elementary, secondary, higher secondary or university level of education.
- 4) A study needs to undertaken on a larger sample, and for a longer durations to examine the effects so that results can be confirmed better on non-cognitive variable like social adaptation traits or some 187 other personality variable which take more time to bring about a change.

- 5) A study by developing program on cybercrime can be implemented to create awareness on cyber crime

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